

The Freesound API: Advances in Audio Search and Retrieval

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ABSTRACT

This paper showcases the latest advances of the Freesound API, focusing on its updated features for improved access and exploration of community audio content shared on the web. Important advancements include restructured metadata retrieval, integration of audio analysis descriptors for richer, content-based search, and further reliance on Solr search technology for both efficient metadata-based querying and vector search. The API introduces a streamlined query system to combine metadata and content-based queries, new similarity spaces that enable more precise sound retrieval, and a unified, easy naming scheme for all audio analysis descriptors. This system is designed to support a range of creative applications, including live performance, browser-based composition tools, educational uses, and generally sound exploration. We overview the new features, demonstrating how users can leverage the API to build more sophisticated audio applications and workflows, and how on-line sound collections can be utilized for accessible and flexible creative work.

1. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

The Freesound API is an HTTP-based web service that allows third-party applications to interact with the Freesound online sound database¹ for purposes such as search, content retrieval, and sound analysis [4]. It currently handles approximately 10.8 million requests per month, reflecting the large-scale access to sound data. The Freesound API is adopted across a range of creative and production contexts, including its integration into digital audio workstations (e.g. Ardour², Soundtrap³), sound library management tools (e.g. Soundly⁴), and a growing ecosystem of plugins and standalone creative coding projects⁵.

Recent updates to the API consolidate previously separate resources, resulting in a more streamlined interface for

accessing both metadata and audio descriptors. Due to technical limitations at the time of development, we relied on two separate databases for metadata search and content search. As a result, it was possible to filter sounds either by metadata attributes (such as `title`, `tags`, `category`, `license`, or `uploader`) or by acoustic characteristics (such as `pitch`, `bpm`, `dissonance`, or `spectral energy`). In order to retrieve all sounds that matched both types of criteria, a combined search existed, but it was computationally intensive and full recall of all matching sounds could not be guaranteed due to the constraints of merging results from two queries. At the core of the updated Freesound API is the enhanced *text search* resource, now renamed to *search*. This resource allows users to directly retrieve sounds not only based on conventional metadata but also based on indexed low-, mid-, and high-level audio descriptors. Audio descriptors are integrated into the searchable index and can be filtered via the same unified interface. This approach eliminates the need for separate *content search* and *combined search* endpoints, both of which have been removed.

Filtering based on audio descriptors operates at the level of scalar descriptor fields, allowing users to specify values for aggregated features, such as `pitch` or `brightness`, as well as categorical values for string-based descriptors, such as `MIDI note`. Results can be filtered by single values or value ranges (e.g. `pitch = [840, 880]` Hz). The indexed audio descriptors are selected features extracted from each sound on the backend, capturing the sound’s main characteristics. The current set comprises a wide range of spectral, temporal, and tonal descriptors, as shown in Table 1. In addition to the listed descriptors, higher-level descriptors are available that capture semantic (e.g. categories, sources, detected events) and perceptual (e.g. overall quality) aspects that extend beyond acoustic-focused properties. Descriptor names have been simplified compared to earlier versions of the API, and are now accessed as concise feature names rather than hierarchical feature paths (e.g. `lowlevel.pitch.mean` → `pitch`). The multi-dimensional (e.g. `tristimulus`) or variable-length descriptors (e.g. `onset times`) are accessible through the API for describing and analyzing audio content, alongside the set of scalar, indexed features used for filtering. Full documentation of the descriptors, including concise explanations and indicative value ranges, is available via the API documentation on the Freesound web interface.

In addition, the updated API introduces integrated sound similarity search directly within the *search* resource. Users may sort search results by similarity to a given sound, combining both descriptor proximity and metadata-based filter-

¹<https://freesound.org/>

²<https://ardour.org>

³<https://www.soundtrap.com>

⁴<http://www.getsoundly.com>

⁵<https://labs.freesound.org/tag/freesound-api/>

Table 1: Audio descriptors available in Freesound.

Descriptor	Descriptor	Descriptor
amplitude_peak_ratio	inharmonic	spectralCentroid
beat_count	log_attack_time	spectralComplexity
beat_loudness	loopable	spectralCrest
beat_times	loudness	spectralEnergy
boominess	mfcc	spectralEntropy
bpm	note_confidence	spectralFlatness
bpm_confidence	note_midi	spectralRolloff
brightness	note_name	spectralSkewness
chord_count	onset_count	spectralSpread
chord_progression	onset_times	start_time
decay_strength	pitch	temporalCentroid
depth	pitch_max	temporalCentroidRatio
dissonance	pitch_min	temporalDecrease
duration	pitch_salience	temporalSkewness
duration_effective	pitch_var	temporalSpread
dynamic_range	reverbness	tonality
hardness	roughness	tonality_confidence
hpcp	sharpness	tristimulus
hpcp_crest	silence_rate	warmth
hpcp_entropy	single_event	zero_crossing_rate

ing. The new architecture supports multiple precomputed latent spaces for defining similarity, allowing users to select the most suitable space based on their preferences. This enables to execute more tailored queries that consider both acoustic and semantic characteristics of sounds, as well as different relationships between them. For example, similarity spaces are derived from acoustic descriptors (vector representations based on combined audio features), semantically informed embeddings such as CLAP [3], or more perceptual frameworks like the Broad Sound Taxonomy [1], which is also Freesound’s organizational scheme.

Lastly, we introduce the option to apply random search to retrieve a randomized subset of results—not only for initial queries but also after applying filters. For example, one can filter by a Freesound `category`⁶ (e.g. *Sound effects*→*Animals*) to retrieve random sounds that might otherwise be overlooked, improving collection discoverability.

These changes are designed to provide a more consistent and simplified interface, which increases the expressive power of search queries through unified descriptor-metadata indexing. As a result, searching, analyzing, and interacting with the Freesound database becomes more efficient and flexible for exploring content.

2. TECHNICAL DETAILS

The updated Freesound API builds on a restructured backend infrastructure, where two previously separate systems (i.e. metadata-based search and audio content-based search) are now combined into a single system (see details below). This new design prioritizes speed, maintainability, and future scalability of the API, while still offering the core functionality needed for audio-based retrieval tasks. The API is accessible via RESTful HTTP requests, and its usage is fully documented⁷. Token-based and OAuth2⁸ remain the

⁶<https://freesound.org/help/faq/#the-broad-sound-taxonomy>

⁷<https://freesound.org/docs/api/>

⁸<https://oauth.net/2/>

standard authentication mechanisms, ensuring secure access for registered applications. Several client libraries are available for interacting with the Freesound API, including official clients in Python, JUCE (C++), and JavaScript, as well as various third-party clients for languages and frameworks such as Common Lisp, Max/MSP, Perl, SuperCollider, Objective-C (iOS), Qt (C++), and Scala.

Our previous search system indexed sound metadata using Apache Solr⁹ and audio content descriptors using Gaia¹⁰, an in-house library for large-scale vector search. This solution provided advanced functionalities for both metadata and descriptor domains, but the combination of the two separate indexes had important limitations (see Section 1). With recent Solr versions supporting vector search, we now solely rely on a single index that includes both metadata and audio descriptors. As mentioned above, this also enables complex queries that combine audio similarity sorting with metadata- or descriptor-based filtering. Audio features are extracted at upload time using the Essentia library [2], and integrated directly into the search index. In addition to Essentia descriptors, our analysis pipeline also supports other analysis frameworks that can be easily integrated into Freesound, with their generated descriptors available in the search index. Post-processing is applied to context-dependent descriptors to handle cases where they may not be meaningful. For example, a descriptor like `chord progression` is set to 0 (or Null) when the sound `category` is not *Music*. In certain cases, the output of audio analyzers generates complex data such as frame-level descriptors which are not indexed in the search system, but remain accessible through the API.

Technical requirements for the WAC 2025 demo: We will require a table for a laptop, access to speakers via mini-jack, and a power outlet. A stable internet connection is necessary for interacting with the Freesound API in real time.

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⁹<https://solr.apache.org/>

¹⁰<https://github.com/MTG/gaia>